

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. This article describes the specific aspects of the development of sustainable tourism, its role in the world and national economies, the problems of developing sustainable tourism, and the increasing negative aspects of the environmental impact of this industry. In Uzbekistan, including in the Khorezm region, tourism is one of the driving sectors of the economy and one of the promising sectors.

Keywords: tourism potential of Khorezm region, sustainable tourism, tourist objects, problems in the field of tourism, services provided to tourists.

Introduction. Uzbekistan has adopted the national goals of sustainable development within the framework of the global goals of sustainable development adopted by the UN and is implementing economic reforms within the framework of achieving these national goals. In order to achieve the goals of sustainable development, effective reforms are being carried out in the country's economic sectors. In particular, one of the driving and promising sectors of the country's economy is tourism.

Literature review. The concept of sustainable tourism was developed to achieve certain goals. These goals are mentioned in the various definitions of sustainable tourism. One well-known example is the definition of the WTO:

“Sustainable tourism development meets the needs of present tourists and host regions while protecting and enhancing opportunity for the future. It is envisaged as leading to management of all resources in such a way that economic, social, and aesthetic needs can be fulfilled while maintaining cultural integrity, essential ecological processes, biological diversity, and life support system” [1].

The mission of the concept of sustainable tourism means the main goal and the priority tasks arising from it, which are aimed at determining the socially responsible attitude in the use of tourist resources and determining measures to prevent damage to the environmental protection of tourism [2].

Data and methodology. Of course, the development of tourism is an objective necessity and important socio-economic value for each area and region. In order to reduce its impact on the environment and nature, we suggest applying the principles of sustainable tourism and green tourism. "Sustainable tourism" is the use of available resources and services of tourism without harming the nature and social environment and the continuous growth of the tourism industry. Sustainable tourism is mainly based on 3 principles:

- 1) preservation of the natural environment, in which the tourism industry should not harm the environment during its development.
- 2) socio-cultural, in which tourists should respect local customs, traditions and values, local residents should receive income from regional tourism.
- 3) ensuring the effective operation of economic, all economic processes, in which all interested parties should see socio-economic benefits.

Result. The terms “sustainable tourism” and “green tourism” are new terms in the literature, and still many authors use them interchangeably. That is, “green tourism” is defined as “sustainable tourism”. However, the author states that “green tourism” is a part of “sustainable tourism”, and “sustainable tourism” is a broader concept than “green tourism”. In “green tourism” only the use of tourism without harming the environment, the effective and harmless use of recreation

resources, and "sustainable tourism" is not only the use of tourism without harming the environment, free from environmental hazards, perhaps, its macroeconomic and territorial, microeconomic, all effective growth of tourism industries in all regions is also understood.

Tourism is one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy, an important source of foreign exchange earnings and jobs, and is closely related to the social, economic and environmental well-being of many countries, especially developing countries. Because tourism connects people with nature, sustainable tourism has a unique ability to promote environmental responsibility and conservation.

According to the World Tourism Organization, sustainable tourism is defined as "tourism that fully considers its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts while meeting the needs of tourists, the tourism industry, the environment and the host community".

You often hear that there is no clear definition of sustainable tourism and that everyone understands it differently. But strictly speaking, this is a way of managing tourism projects, in which all the good and valuable things remain in that form for the generations after us. Business travel, family holidays, ecotourism - can be sustainable if it meets certain criteria that support sustainable development. Sustainable tourism is not a "type" of tourism and does not occur in specific places, but rather a spirit of organizational management and decision-making.

Support and build capacity for sustainable tourism activities that promote environmental protection, conservation and protection of wildlife, flora, biodiversity, ecosystems and cultural diversity and lead to increased prosperity and incomes in local communities and development of local economies , it is also necessary to improve human settlements and the natural environment in general.

The Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC) is a universal body that supports and coordinates the development of sustainable tourism both globally and regionally. This body has adopted various programs in order to protect the natural development of biosystems on a global scale. For example, in order to restore the natural environment in the Galapagos Islands, the number of annual tourist flows was set at 12,000 visits, but later this number was changed by the Ecuadorian government to 50,000 visits for economic purposes.

The concept of sustainable tourism means a set of forms, methods and means of tourism development and management that do not conflict with the environment, cultural values, and the interests of the local population's lifestyle. The scientific-theoretical structure of the concept of sustainable tourism is based on the methodological approach that summarizes the 17 goals of sustainable development promoted by the United Nations. The priority areas of activity based on the concept of sustainable tourism include the following (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Specific aspects of applying the concept of sustainable tourism

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- to assess the capacities of reception and accommodation of tourist infrastructure objects;
- taking into account the influence of economic, social and cultural factors in the management process of tourist companies;
- determining the competence of employees of the hospitality industry regarding the principles of sustainable tourism;
- determining the optimal standards of resource consumption and consumption in tourism planning at the macro-, meso- and microeconomic level;
- establishment of interstate and interregional technology transfer related to tourism;
- to ensure compatibility of demographic parameters with the consumption characteristics of the proposed tourist product in the tourist coverage of service facilities;
- aim to contribute to the environmental protection and economical use of resources in the process of development of tourist products, to increase the well-being of local residents of the receiving side of tourists;
- elimination of differences between regions in tourism development;
- use of state and private sector partnerships in the implementation of strategic tourism development programs.

Conclusion. Clarifying the systematic advantages of applying the concept of sustainable tourism will help to implement programs related to the development of tourism at the level of the state and corporations. It should be noted that in the strategic development of regional markets of services, attention to the application of the concept of sustainable tourism is emerging as a demand of the times.

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